

Leucaena as green leaf manure for lowland rice

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Leucaena leucocephala is a renewable source of green manure. On dry basis, the tender loppings contain 4.3% N. We tested the contribution of 10 t leucaena/ha to growth and yield of IR20 using 4 levels of N (0, 50, 75, and 100 kg/ha) during rabi 1986-87, in 3 replications. Soil was clay loam with 0.06% total N, low Olsen's P (8.6 kg/ha), 70 ppm exchangeable K, pH 7.4, CEC 18.6 meq/100 g, and 0.34% organic C.

Fresh tender loppings of 50-d-old leucaena (Hawaiian Giant Var. K8) harvested from 2-yr-old plants were

Effect of leucaena as green leaf manure on growth characters, yield components, and grain yield of rice (IR20). Madurai, India, 1986-87 rabi.

Treatment	Growth character		Yield component				Grain yield (t/ha)
	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain (g)	
No N	72.2	5.8	4.2	18.62	78.0	16.42	2.8
Leucaena at 10 t/ha	82.6	8.0	5.8	19.76	93.2	18.60	3.6
50 kg N/ha alone	83.0	7.8	6.0	19.86	92.6	18.64	3.6
50 kg N/ha + leucaena	92.4	8.8	8.0	20.64	105.6	19.56	4.3
75 kg N/ha alone	91.4	8.6	7.2	20.52	99.8	18.78	4.0
75 kg N/ha + leucaena	97.4	10.2	9.8	21.32	110.2	20.74	4.8
100 kg N/ha alone	93.8	9.2	8.2	20.96	104.6	19.68	4.3
LSD (0.05)	3.1	0.7	1.1	0.46	3.9	0.78	0.4

incorporated 10 d before planting rice. A basal dose of 22 kg P, 41.5 kg K, and 50% of N was applied just before planting; the rest of N was topdressed in 2 equal splits 30 and 40 d after transplanting.

Leucaena as leaf manure combined

with fertilizer N at suboptimal levels increased growth and yield over suboptimal N alone (see table). Leucaena with 75 kg N/ha gave highest grain yield (4.8 t/ha), better than that with 100 kg N/ha (4.3 t/ha). Applying 50 kg N with leucaena gave 4.3 t/ha. □

Fertilizer requirement of rice - rice - green manure cropping system

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We assessed the fertilizer requirements of rice - rice - green manure, a major

cropping system in Central Kerala, at RARS, Pattambi, 1983 to 1986.

Green manure *Sesbania speciosa* was raised (Feb-May) and incorporated before the kharif crop (Jan-Sep), at 4.3 t/ha (21.1% dry matter, 2.4% N, 0.31% P, and 1.42% K). The rabi crop (Sep-Jan) was given no organic manure. The kharif and rabi rices (Jaya variety) were given 50, 75, and 100% of the fertilizer dose 90-45-45 kg NPK/ha. The sandy loam soil contained 1.38% organic C, 0.025% available N, 19.1 kg

available P, and 222.3 kg available K/ha. The pH was 5.4 and cation exchange capacity 12.6 meq/100 g soil.

The treatment receiving 75% of the fertilizer dose in each season yielded the same as that receiving 100% (see table). □

Effect of fertilizer treatments on grain and straw yields of rice - rice - green manure cropping system. Pattambi, Kerala, India, 1983-86.

Treatment	Percentage of fertilizer dose		Mean grain yield (t/ha)			Mean straw yield (t/ha)		
	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi	Total for the system	Kharif	Rabi	Total for the system
T ₁	100	100	3.3	3.8	7.1	2.9	3.2	6.1
T ₂	100	75	3.1	3.6	6.7	3.0	3.0	6.0
T ₃	100	50	2.8	3.6	6.4	3.1	3.0	6.1
T ₄	75	100	2.9	4.1	7.0	3.0	3.4	6.4
T ₅	75	75	3.2	3.7	6.9	3.0	3.1	6.1
T ₆	75	50	3.2	3.1	6.3	2.5	2.3	4.8
T ₇	50	100	3.0	3.7	6.7	2.6	3.0	5.6
T ₈	50	75	3.1	3.4	6.5	2.5	2.5	5.0
T ₉	50	50	2.9	3.4	6.3	2.8	2.7	5.5
LSD (0.05)					0.4			0.6

Effect of rice plants on fertilizer N losses in flooded soil

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We evaluated the influence of rice plants on fertilizer N losses from flooded soil in greenhouse experiments in 1986-87 with planted (variety M201) and unplanted treatments. Five kg of Myers clay soil (pH 6.6, 0.1% total N) in 1986, and 3 kg of Sacramento clay soil (pH 7.7, 0.1% total N) in 1987 were weighed into plastic pots after air-drying and screening.

Solutions of ¹⁵N-labeled KNO₃ and urea were separately mixed with soil